

Synthesis and Antiinflammatory Activity of Substituted 2-Amino-4-carboxy-5-thiazoleacetic Acids

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Acidic non-steroidal antiinflammatory drugs (NS-AIDs) characteristically possess a cationic site, an aromatic hydrophobic region and a lipophilic/aromatic moiety at an out-of-plane angle¹. These generally fit in the classical receptor models of Scherrer² and Shen³. In most of the clinically used acidic drugs the cationic site is an aromatic carboxyl as in salicylates or fenamates or an acetate (or 2-methylacetate) as in the acetates and propionates.

Thiazoleacetic acids exhibit significant antiinflammatory activity, e.g. 2-(4-chlorophenyl)-4-thiazoleacetic acid⁴ and 2-phenyl-4-(4-chlorophenyl)-5-thiazoleacetic acid⁵ are reported as equally or more active than phenylbutazone; the former (frenclazic acid) was used clinically but later withdrawn because of its hepatotoxicity⁶. Recently⁷ some benzophenone dicarboxylic acids possessing an aryl and an acetic carboxyl have shown significant inhibitory activity against leukotriene-B₄, which has been implicated as potential mediators of inflammation; both acidic sites have been considered necessary for significant activity.

The 4-carboxy-5-thiazoleacetic acids (5) have the classical hydrophobic aromatic region, a phenyl ring at an angle and also both an aryl and an acetic carboxyl as cationic sites. These compounds were prepared by condensation of ethyl β -bromo- α -ketoglutarate⁸ and substituted phenylthioureas⁹ (prepared from amines and ammonium thiocyanate with concentrated HCl), and hydrolysing the esters. The corresponding unsubstituted compounds and

the acetate derivative was prepared by the reported method⁸. All the compounds were evaluated for their antiinflammatory activity by the carrageenan paw edema method^{10,11}. The esters were found to be much more active than the corresponding acids, and the presence of an aryl unit greatly enhanced the activity.

Experimental

Ethyl α -ketoglutarate (1) was prepared by the Fischer-Speier esterification of the ketoglutaric acid¹².

Ethyl- β -bromo- α -ketoglutarate (2): Bromine (2.75 g) in carbon tetrachloride (6 ml) was added dropwise over 20 min to ethyl α -ketoglutarate (3.6 g) with stirring at 15–20°. The reaction mixture was stirred for an additional 2 h, then the solvent removed and the bromoester distilled at 121–27°/3 mm (lit.⁶ 107–08°/1 mm), (5.1 g) (Found : Br, 28.2 (Stepanow). C₉H₁₃O₅Br requires : Br, 28.43%; λ_{max} 305 nm (lit.⁸ 305 nm).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL, SPECTRAL AND ANTIINFLAMMATORY ACTIVITY (A.A.) DATA OF COMPOUNDS 4-8

Compd. no.	R	R'	Yield %	M.p. °C	λ_{\max} nm	ν_{\max} cm^{-1}	A.A. %
4a	Ph	Et	74	80-83	219, 271, 306	3 320, 1 740, 1 690	54
b	4-ClPh	Et	67	125-27	219, 276, 313	3 360, 1 735, 1 1710	77
c	3-ClPh	Et	70	133-34	220, 273, 309	3 310, 1 730, 1 715	70
d	2-ClPh	Et	67	Oil	220, 275, 305	3 400, 1 740, 1 710	68
e	3-MeOPh	Et	60	92-94	219, 271, 315	3 340, 1 720-1 700	51
5a	4-ClPh	H	67	192-93d	219, 274, 309		47
b	3-ClPh	H	61	216d	221, 274, 305	3 490, 2 900, 1 710-1 690	33
6	H	Et	88	125-26			28
7	H	H	86	197-96			12
8	COMe	Et	82	149-51	219,257	3 450, 1 735, 1 710	47
Indomethein (dose 4 mg/kg)							59

Ethyl 4-ethoxycarbonyl-2-(3-chlorophenyl)aminothiazole-5-acetate (4c): A mixture of *m*-chlorophenylthiourea (1.06 g), ethyl β -bromo- α -ketoglutarate (1.6 g) and alcohol (15 ml) was refluxed for 8 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled in ice, neutralised by slow addition of a saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate to yield **4c** which was washed and crystallised from carbon tetrachloride-petroleum ether (b.p.60-80°), (1.1 g), m.p. 133-34° (Found : C, 51.96; H, 4.55; N, 7.68; S, 8.86; Cl, 9.50. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_2\text{SO}_4\text{C}$ requires : C, 52.10; H, 4.65; N, 7.60; S, 8.69; Cl, 9.61 %); λ_{\max} (MeOH) 220, 275 and 305 nm; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 310 (NH), 1 730 and 1 715 cm^{-1} (CO acetate and aromatic carboxylate).

The *o*-chloro compound (**4d**) did not crystallise and was purified by column chromatography over a neutral alumina column with 4% methanol-benzene as eluant.

Similarly, the other compounds (**4a**, **b**, **d**, **e**) were prepared (Table 1).

4-Carboxy-2-(3-chlorophenyl)-5-thiazoleacetic acid (5b): The ester (**4c**; 2.6 g) was refluxed for 10 h with 4*N* HCl (7 ml). The ester gradually went into solution (2-3 h). The solution was evaporated to near dryness on a water-bath, the residue dissolved in saturated sodium bicarbonate solution, filtered to remove insoluble impurities, and the filtrate neutralised with dilute HCl to

yield **5b** which was crystallised from water containing some DMF, (0.17 g), m.p. 216-17 (Found : C; 45.83; H, 2.56; N, 8.75; S, 10.06; Cl, 11.11. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}$ requires : C, 46.08; H, 2.90; N, 8.96; S, 10.25; Cl, 11.34%); λ_{\max} (MeOH) 221, 274 and 312 nm; ν_{\max} 3 390 (NH), 2 930br (OH of acid), 1 710-1 690br (two acid functions). Similarly, the 5-thiazoleacetic acid (**5a**) was prepared.

The 2-aminoester (**6**), m.p. 125° (lit⁸. 124-25); the acid (**7**), m.p. 196° (lit⁸. 194.5-195); and the 2-acetylaminoester (**8**), m.p. 149-50° (lit⁸. 152-153.5) were obtained by the reported method⁸.

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NOTE

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